

Analysing Crop Yield Patterns on the Arable Land Using XAI

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Abstract. Many different machine learning models have been successfully applied for crop yield forecasting, an increasingly important and popular problem in recent years due to the growing need for ensuring food security globally. The way the predictions are derived by the machine learning models is not directly evident. Providing explanations for the decision-making process, apart from increasing transparency of the model, can be beneficial in many contexts. One of them is a comprehensive understanding of spatial field variability, as some parts of a field produce more relative to the rest of the field. This study aims to provide explanations for yield fluctuations within the field by employing a technique from the domain of eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), known as SHAP (Shapley Additive Attribution Method). The experimental part involves three phases, training the machine-learning model, generating a post-hoc explanation model on the sample (pixel) level, and aggregating obtained explanations by taking into consideration spatial aspects of the pixels. Experiments are conducted on commercial wheat fields utilizing pixel-level yield monitoring data. Several machine learning regression models are trained by using vegetation indices (NDMI, NDVI, GNDVI, DVI, EVI, GCI, SAVI etc.) across crop-growth stages jointly with soil and physical-geographical properties. The models are evaluated and the best one is chosen as relevant for the other two phases. For analysis, the yield values are divided into four categories: low, medium-low, medium-high, and high yield. In the first aggregation, the obtained explanations are used to understand the main features of the decision-making process of the machine learning model per each field. Results show that GNDVI in the critical phase of the wheat growing season (grain filling in May) is the most important feature for most fields, excluding two fields, where the most influential features are DVI and GCI in the same growing phase. Accordingly, it

can be concluded that the values of several vegetation indices for the critical growing phase of wheat have a major effect on the decision-making process of the machine learning yield prediction model. To dive more into the decision-making process and spatial yield variability, the explanations are firstly aggregated for correctly and wrongly predicted yields per each yield category. The analysis for one field discovered that the wrong decisions can be attributed to the high values of the top 3 rated features, where high values of GNDVI and GCI lead to overestimation of low and medium-low yield. For correct predictions of these two yield categories, explanation plots indicate that low values of GNDVI, GCI, and DVI are main contributors to low yield correct classification. Similarly, for some other fields, it is observed that GNDVI and GCI contribute to the correct decision for all yield categories. The underestimation of the model for fields with predominantly high yield and medium-high yield categories can be explained by high silt consistency. These examples demonstrate the potential of using XAI methods to conclude the main factors for spatial crop yield variability that can be used during the season for actionable decisions.

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